

LINGUISTIC AGGRESSION AS A TYPE OF EMOTIONAL RESPONSE

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Annotatsiya. Mazkur ilmiy maqolada verbal (og'zaki) agressiyaning ingliz adabiyotida ishlatilishi, bir-biriga semantik, pragmatik aloqaga kirishishiga ko'ra xususiyatlariga ko'ra o'xshashlik va farqlari tahlil qilinadi. Shuningdek aggressiv hatti-harakatni vujudga kelishi, uni verbal holatda amalga oshirilishidagi vositalar hamda aggressiyaning insonga psixik ta'siri, aggressiyadan keying holati lingvistik jihatdan tahlil qilingan. Bundan tashqari verbal aggressiyaning jazolash kabi turlari, ushbu turlarga tegishli bo'lgan hatti-harakatlarni ifodalovchi misollar, ularning qo'llanilishida aggressivlik darajasining oshishi yoki pasayishi misollar bilan ochib berishga harakat qilingan. Ingliz tillidagi verbal aggressiv iboralar solishtirilib tahlil qilingan va ularning qo'llanilishidagi farq va o'xshashliklar ochib berilishiga harakat qilingan.

Kalit so'zlar: *tajovuzkorlik, hissiy munosabat, og'zaki, og'zaki bo'lmagan, xulq-atvor, shaxsning o'ziga xosligi, noroziligi, o'ziga xosligi, o'ziga xosligi semantik leksemalar*

Annotation. This scientific article analyzes the similarities and differences of verbal (oral) aggression English literature according to their characteristics, semantic and pragmatic connections. The emergence of aggressive behavior, methods of its verbal implementation, the psychological impact of aggression on a person, and the situation after aggression are also analyzed linguistically. In addition, an attempt was made to identify types of verbal aggression such as punishment, examples of behavior related to these types, and examples of increases or decreases in the level of aggression when using them. Verbal aggressive phrases in English language were compared and analyzed, and an attempt was made to identify differences and similarities in their use.

Key words: *aggressiveness, emotional reaction, verbal, non-verbal, behavior, person's consciousness, disapproval, chew the target out, lexemes-identifiers, semantic lexemes.*

Human behavior, as a rule, is characterized by the presence of certain emotional components that reflect his inner state, as well as his attitude to the surrounding world and people. The presence of an emotional component of behavior is motivated mainly by the situation in which the individual is.

The development of aggressiveness in language and speech is greatly influenced by social processes that, changing a person's consciousness, as well as his emotional sphere, form his language, culture of behavior and culture of speech.

The importance of information as a means of carrying out a certain ideology has caused the distortion of reality by the mass media (mass media) in all countries of the world, including Britain, Uzbekistan and Russia. It is this factor that is reflected in the interpretation of events taking place in the world in gloomy tones with a hint of hostility and hatred, as well as hostile, a very aggressive modality of media texts of both cultures, often having a direct and rude manifestation.

Numerous and diverse emotional reactions accompany the communication process and manifest themselves in the form of emotionally expressive, mimic and pantomime movements, which, as a rule, are descriptive in the text. At the same time, nonverbal aggressive reactions accompanying interpersonal communication represent its paralinguistic component [Горелов 2006:14], which, similarly to linguistic means of communication,

“Leave me,” said a **stern voice** behind him [Wilde, 2002:134].

The presented statement illustrates a descriptive way of conveying the speaker's disapproval, as evidenced by the stern lexeme, denoting “something that someone says or does that expresses **disapproval**” [Longman, 2003:1414] and used as a characteristic of the speaker's voice. Another example:

— *Sen hali shoshmay turgin! — dedi oyim **dag'dag'a** qilib!* [To'xtaboyev, 2010:7]

In the example, there is a description of the irritated speech of the hero using the verb "dag'dag'a", meaning "menace". It is obvious that the hero is deeply dissatisfied with the situation. The exclamation mark, as the most emotional graphic sign of the punctuation system of the language, as a rule, indicates the strength of emotion. Moreover, the analysis of the prosodic characteristics of the hero's speech, transmitted in a descriptive way, allows us to conclude about its suddenness and loudness, which is confirmed in the definition of this verb. Any cry always implies an emotional explosion and the release of one or another positive or negative emotion.

Based on the importance of all types of emotional response, we will nevertheless analyze the linguistic side of emotions and feelings, since they are of particular interest from the point of view of their embodiment by means of language and speech. So, for example:

LIZA. *Oh, Freddy, a taxi. The very thing.*
FREDDY. **But, damn it, I've no money** [Shaw, 2001:120].

In this example, the emotion of irritation associated with the situation of the hero's lack of money for a taxi is embodied. His use of the colloquial interjective exclamation **damn it** in speech indicates the strength of emotion, as, of course, is evidenced by the dictionary definition of the interjective exclamation **damn it** – "used to show that you are annoyed or disappointed" [Shaw, 2001:339].

However, the emotional state of the speaker is not limited only to irritation. It is obvious that it is combined with the emotion of disappointment, as evidenced by the use of the conjunction **but**, which, according to functional grammar, expresses an opposition indicating that the speaker has a complex emotion of irritation-disappointment. In the given example, the emotion of irritation-frustration, conveyed by the interjection exclamation **damn it**, is amplified not only by the contrastive conjunction **but**, but also by syntactically-framed commas, in which the interjection exclamation is included. A comma, as a rule, indicates a pause in the speaker's speech; in the example we have indicated, it separates the lexemes **but** and **damn it**. Note that the **but** token indicates the existence of an obstacle, and the comma following it is necessary for the author to create a kind of intrigue necessary to keep the interlocutor in a state of uncertainty associated with the impossibility of subsequent actions of the speaker. Therefore, the post-pause realization of irritation – **damn it - I'll kill you!** – he **shouted** and, **grabbing** a marble board from the table with a force still unknown to him, took a step towards it and **swung** at it.

The volume of speech, intonation, lexical structure, and syntactic organization of the duplicate of the aggressor are all external manifestations of hostility that are determined by the interior aspect. The word "**stand up**" - "*assume a standing position*" [Longman, 2003:1231], expresses the order in the text fragment, and its infinitive grammatical form denotes the imperative mood. While the verb "**stand up**" is repeated in the hero's replicas, there is a clear intonation difference between these replicas, and the first is somewhat of a placeholder before the second is put into practice:

- *Get up!* I yelled, "*Get up!*" in a quiet but stern voice.

The inclusion of the most emotive graphic sign—the exclamation mark—indicates that the lexeme "**stand up**" in both instances is marked by a certain level of emotionality. However, you may determine the difference in the intensity of the angry feeling felt by the speaker by comparing the syntactic structures of two copies of "**Stand up!**" (one exclamation mark) and "**Stand up!!!**" (three exclamation marks). In other words, the second replica's inclusion of three exclamation marks signifies a triple intonation amplification. The final replica yelled, "**Get up!**" loudly. The speech volume scale reveals that it is at a greater level because the addressee has lost control of his emotions. As a result, in the text fragment, the speaker's violent reaction's exterior aspect comes through in both the lexical structure of his statements and his intonation traits, or the power and volume of his voice.

Initially, it is important to acknowledge that verbal and non-verbal aggressiveness include a range of emotions that varied in intensity, spanning from the least potent to the most potent. Therefore, it is important to consider the level of severity when characterizing hostile feelings. [Виллюнас, 1993:166].

For example,

*"You are **mad**, Dorian."*

"Ah! I was waiting for you to call me Dorian."

*"You are **mad**" [Wilde, 2002:304]*

The text fragment illustrates the hero's aggression of medium intensity, which manifests itself in the condemnation of the addressee, implemented through the lexical repetition of **mad**, and does not imply physical violence against the object.

Moreover, aggression, as well as the intensity of its expression, like any other type of emotional response, can certainly be both controlled and uncontrolled. Let us note such an important characteristic of verbal and non-verbal aggression as awareness (purposefulness) / unawareness of the corresponding actions. Let us note that by conscious verbal and nonverbal aggression we understand actions that are characterized by the presence of an internal urge to cause harm to the recipient, while the unconscious variety of the type of emotional response under study does not imply the presence of such an urge.

For example:

Higgins (in despairing wrath outside). What the devil I have done with my slippers? (He appears at the door.)

*Liza (**snatching** up the slippers, and hurling them at him one after the other with all her force). There are your slippers. And there. Take your slippers; and may you never have a day's luck with them! [Shaw, 2001:108].*

Thus, making a conclusion, the analysis of aggressive reactions indicates to us the possibility of attributing verbal and nonverbal aggression to the types of emotional response. Thus, we observe the substitution of the inner feeling (envy) by an external emotion (contempt), which are represented in the analyzed statement. At the same time, verbal and non-verbal aggression includes a variety of a) aggressive emotions: disapproval, irritation, anger, etc.; b) negative feelings: disgust, envy, contempt, etc., as well as c) affects: stupor, loss of self-control, etc. Moreover, any aggressive manifestation of emotions, feelings and affective states has a different embodiment in language and speech, which is reflected in the lexical and semantic system, grammatical and syntactic structures, as well as in the use of many stylistic techniques.

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